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"HOMEWORK ONLINE" AS AN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article raises the problem of reducing the completion of homework in a foreign language, as one of the main ways to consolidate the material obtained in a practical lesson, control and self-control. Using the Internet service Learningapps.org The author suggests an experiment on the topic of "Homework online" with a group of students; which contributed to the popularization of homework among students, increased the percentage of knowledge quality and developed the skill of working with information.

Keywords: *Internet service; online homework; Learningapps.*

Introduction:

It is difficult to argue with the fact that homework is a necessary element of the educational process, especially in a foreign language, as it helps the student to strengthen the acquired knowledge and is a powerful tool for control and self-control.

But, unfortunately, the role of homework has greatly decreased over the past decades, and at the moment many students do not have the proper motivation to do it. It is often easier for students to use ready-made answer forms or copy from their classmates, which leads to a loss of importance of homework in the educational process.

The new generation, the children of the digital age, want the school to speak the same language with them and digital technologies are one of the ways to communicate. In this regard, one of the main reasons for children's lack of motivation for homework is the retrograde ways of doing it. I conducted a survey among students from 2nd to 10th grade; they

were asked to answer the question: would they be interested in getting homework online, through some network resources. The expected result was the overwhelming prevalence of supporters of this idea, which prompted me to conduct an experiment on the introduction of online homework in a foreign language using an Internet service.

To implement the experiment, the following preliminary stages were worked out:

- analysis of thematic planning, for which Internet services will be used;
- planning of universal educational activities of students;
- formation of goals for the use of network services (study of new material, consolidation, generalization of material, control);
- analysis and selection of effective types of Internet services;
- creating tasks for students to practice on the service and step-by-step instructions for working with it on the YouTube video hosting;
- the introduction of Internet services into educational activities as a test material in the classroom to familiarize students with the service itself and how to work with it;
- experimental implementation as a homework assignment;

The ultimate goal of this experiment was to introduce online homework as a permanent element of the educational system in foreign language lessons.

After analyzing the Internet resources recommended for training, I chose an Internet service Learningapps.org .

This service was created to support the learning process through interactive applications.

The service also provides the opportunity to share the finished product via social networks, web links and QR codes.

This service also contributes to the implementation of the following modern educational technologies:

1. Multi-level training, which allows you to help a weak student and pay attention to a strong one.
2. Information and computer technologies that allow a person to adapt more successfully and faster to the environment and ongoing social changes
3. Health-saving technology, which, through the introduction of interactivity, ensures the physical and psychological well-being of students.
4. Game methods that broaden horizons, develop cognitive activity, form certain skills and abilities necessary in practical activities.

How can we use them in a foreign language lesson? In fact, everything is limited only by your imagination.

For example, to memorize new words, you can use the game "Find a pair", "Crossword Puzzle", "Find a word", while practicing spelling skills and computer keyboard skills.

Using all kinds of quizzes trains grammar and text skills very well. And with the help of the "audio/video content" template, students practice listening and speaking skills.

The teacher, in turn, has the opportunity to monitor the activity of students on the service and monitor the completion of tasks using summary tables in his personal account. There is also an opportunity for reflection, using a local chat service, where students can discuss certain tasks, both with the teacher and among themselves.

Thus, having completed all the preparatory work, I started experimental activities.

The experiment lasted for a month. I selected children from the same parallel with approximately equal cognitive abilities and divided them into experimental (group No.

1) and control (group No. 2) groups, where the children of group No. 1 received homework via an online resource, and the children of group No. 2 did it in workbooks. The students reacted responsibly to the experiment and actively participated in it.

A test was written based on the results of the topic. After the analysis of the work, the following results were established. The percentage of the quality of the learned material in the module of group No. 1 was 70%, when the control group had only 40%. These results proved that online homework has a beneficial effect on the level of students' knowledge.

At the end of the experiment, the children of group No. 1 asked for the continuation of homework in electronic form, and I, in turn, had the idea of introducing homework via the Internet to group No. 2, and subsequently to other classes.

Thus, analyzing all of the above, I became convinced that by doing homework over the Internet, students spend less of their free time, they do it with pleasure, learn to work with information on their own, develop self-control, get rid of the fear of mistakes, knowing that the test can be redone. I believe that the project "Homework online" can radically change the attitude of students to homework, and also simplify the work of colleagues, so that they do not have to sit on dark nights with stacks of notebooks.

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